

SIMULATION OF IoT BASED HOME AUTOMATION USING ARDUINO

Arun Francis G^[1], Sundar V^[2], Gowtham E^[3]

[1] Assistant Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Karpagam College of Engineering, Coimbatore, India.

[2] Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Karpagam College of Engineering, Coimbatore, India.

[3] Student, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Karpagam College of Engineering, Coimbatore, India.

Correspondence: ja.arunji@gmail.com

Abstract— Home Automation System is one of the subjects that is gaining traction due to its multiple benefits. Home automation is the process of remotely monitoring and controlling household appliances. With the Internet's and its applications' never-ending growth, there is a lot of promise and scope for remote access, control, and monitoring of network-enabled appliances. This article examines a variety of intelligent home automation systems and technologies from a variety of perspectives. The endeavor was focused on the home automation idea, in which smart devices are used to control and monitor operations. Home automation systems and technologies with a central controller (Arduino or Raspberry Pi), cloud-based, Bluetooth-based, SMS-based, ZigBee-based, mobile-based, RF Module-based, web-based, and Internet-based performance are all reviewed. Life is becoming simpler and easier in all aspects due to advancements in automation technologies.

Keywords—Automation system, IoT device, smart home, emerging internet technology, Wireless Controlled Home.

I. INTRODUCTION

Automation devices are widely employed in a range of markets, where they are utilised to regulate a number of process-related operations. We have a proclivity to enter the realm of automation, in which the majority of processes, such as factory automation, home automation, and many businesses, are automated. Home automation is shifting toward mechanization, in which industrial equipment operates various systems in homes with less human work. It uses a variety of technology and controllers on desktops, computers, goods, phones, and tablets to impose autonomous control of home appliances. In this study, we have a tendency to propose a method to modify the residence by utilizing IoT technology. Governments in nations like China are supporting IoT through funding, and there are currently a minimum of nine billion interconnected devices in China, with twenty-four billion devices predicted by 2020. Homes in the twenty-first century can become increasingly self-controlled and automated as a result of their convenience, especially when employed in a very private dwelling. Consumers can use home automation systems to control a variety of electrical items. Wired connectivity is available in several well-known home

automation products. Unless the system is well-planned and executed throughout the actual development of the building, this does not result in a confusion. Deployment prices are skyrocketing, with the exception of pre-existing structures. Wireless networks, on the other hand, are a huge assistance when it comes to automating processes. Wi-Fi and other wireless advancements have advanced. Over time, wireless networks such as Wi-Fi have become more common in home networking. Wireless solutions, such as those used in home and building automation applications, offer a number of benefits that would be impossible to achieve with purely conventional networks. Home automation powered by the Internet of Things is slowly but surely becoming a part of people's daily lives all around the world. In fact, the global market for smart home automation is expected to reach \$40 billion by 2020. The Internet of Things now powers a wide range of devices. Thermostats, refrigerators, security systems, and even dryers and kettles are among them. With the passage of time, additional devices with smarter functions will undoubtedly be added.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

In the current environment, home appliances and devices are controlled through a method that involves manually going up to the device and taking actions. A similar technique is required. As a result, we're putting home automation into practice. This method is then used to track, alter, and transmit data to other computers wirelessly. If special circumstances arise, sophisticated actions can be undertaken right away. As an example, consider a little kettle. The kettle can be configured to shut off automatically once it reaches a particular temperature. It's also possible that the customer receives a notification. The same definition will now apply to everyone in the house as well as all computers. It's a smart home with Internet of Things capabilities. Such chores can be completed with a button click rather of physically walking to the computer and conducting actions.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

It is made up of a power supply unit, an Arduino microcontroller, Wi-Fi electronic equipment, an LED, and RELAYS. Examines the schematic design on the bread board with various ICs, the PCB layout of the schematic tested on the bread board to determine if it conforms to the

target, and draws schematic diagrams on plain paper according to the hardware installation application Finishing and ultimately prepping boards and designed hardware for testing. The machine code is in charge of programming the microcontroller to monitor the functionality of the half-integrated implementation's circuit. For the gift job, we used the Orcad Type Kit for PCB circuit design and Arduino package construction tools, as well as writing and compiling ASCII text code written in the C language. For the gift job, we used the Orcad Type Kit for PCB circuit design and Arduino package building tools, as well as writing and compiling ASCII text code written in the C language. The Atmel Heart includes 32 general-purpose operational registers as well as a beautiful instruction set. Due to the ability to reach two free registers in one clock cycle with a single command, the Arithmetic Logic Unit (ALU) is directly connected to all thirty-two registers. The resulting architecture is more code efficient, allowing for up to ten times better throughput than typical CISC microcontrollers.

IV. MODEL OF THE SYSTEM

Fig. 1. Block Diagram of the Proposed System

a. ARDUINO UNO

High-performance instruction sets with 32 general-purpose operational registers are included in the Atmel

AVR centre. Both of the Arithmetic Logic Unit's (ALU) thirty-two registers have been connected directly, allowing two freelance registers to arrive in one clock cycle during an instruction., 1Kbytes EEPROM, 2Kbytes SRAM, twenty-three general-purpose I/O lines, thirty-two general-purpose operating registers, and a real-time counter.

In Idle mode, the CPU is turned down, but SRAM, timers/counters, SPI sockets, and interrupt mechanisms are active. Before an interrupt or hardware reset, the power-down mode register saves the information but disables all chip functionality. The machine that is not synchronised runs in Power-Saving mode, allowing the user to run a timer while the rest of the system sleeps. To reduce shift noise during ADC transitions, the ADC Noise Reduction mode disables the CPU and all I/O modules except the asynchronous timer and ADC. The crystal / resonator generator is turned on in standby mode, and the rest of the machine is turned off during this period. This allows for a quick start-up with low power usage. As a result, most generators and asynchronous timers remain in prolonged standby mode. Electrical events such as bit keys, sliders, and wheels can be added to AVR microcontrollers using the QTouch library from Atmel. The innovative charge-transfer signal acquisition approach ensures accurate sensing and fully integrates bit key news as well as adjacent key suppression methods for fuzzy keys. Detection of events. It's simple to experiment, design, and test your own bit applications with the QTouch Suite toolchain.

b. ESP8266 WI-FI MODULE

By connecting the ESP8266 to any microcontroller through serial UART and using the normal AT Command set Firmware, or by directly integrating the new firmware with a Wi-Fi-enabled microcontroller. Using the provided SDK, it can be used as is. GPIO pins can be used for analogue and digital IOs, as well as PWM, SPI, and I2C. The ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module is a self-contained system on a chip (SOC) with an integrated TCP/IP protocol stack that allows any microcontroller to connect to your Wi-Fi network. ESP8266 will either host an application or a separate application processor will handle all Wi-Fi networking tasks. Each ESP8266 module comes pre-programmed with AT command set firmware, so you can use an Arduino to connect it to your device, and the same Wi-Fi shield for the Wi-Fi capabilities. Will be able to help. The ESP8266 module is a low-cost board that has a large and rapidly growing user base. The ESP8266 is a low-cost Wi-Fi module that may be used with a UART serial interface to add Wi-Fi connection to a microcontroller project. With the addition of electricity, the module can be reconfigured to work as a stand-alone Wi-Fi system. The ESP8266 module is a TTL "serial over wireless Internet" gadget in a nutshell. Assuming your microcontroller can

communicate with a TTL serial device, as illustrated in the below diagram.

Fig. 2: Wi-Fi Module

c. RELAYS

A relay is a switch that is activated or deactivated by electricity. Some relays use an electromagnet to control the switching device, although alternative operational concepts are also utilised. A relay's principal function is to control a circuit using only a low-power signal. It's also employed in situations where only one signal can operate a large number of circuits. The use of relays dates back to the invention of telephones. They were crucial in the switching of calls in telephone exchanges. Long-distance telegraphy was also possible with them. They were employed to change the direction of a signal from one source to another. They were also utilised to conduct Boolean and other logical processes once computers were invented. Relays in high-end applications require a lot of power to be operated by electric motors and other devices. Contactors are the name for these types of relays. Relays are employed when a low-power signal is required to run a circuit or several circuits must be controlled by a single signal. Relays were first used in long-distance telegraph networks to repeat and re-transmit signals from one circuit to another. In telephone exchanges and early computers, relays were employed to conduct logical processes. A contactor is a type of relay that can handle the high power required to directly operate an electric motor. The state relay monitors an electrical circuit without any moving parts by using a semiconductor chip that is activated by light. To safeguard electrical circuits from overload or flaws, relays with regulated operating characteristics and, in some cases, several operating coils are utilised.; These duties are also fulfilled by digital instruments known as "safety relays" in modern electric power systems. Because the current required to run the relay coil is larger than most chips can provide, a transistor, as shown below, is frequently necessary. BC109C or a similar code should be used. A 4k7 resistor would almost probably enough. The diode is used to short circuit the high voltage "back EMF" as the current flowing through the coil is abruptly halted.

Fig.3: Relay Operation Circuit

d. AC LOAD (BULB)

An incandescent light bulb, lamp, or globe is an electric light that consists of a wire filament that has been heated to a temperature high enough to create visible light. A glass or fused quartz bulb filled with inert gas or a vacuum protects the filament from oxidation. A chemical reaction in a halogen lamp delays filament evaporation by re-depositing metal vapour on the filament, hence increasing its life. Electricity is supplied to the light bulb via feed-through connections or wires put into the glass. The majority of bulbs are housed in sockets, which offer both mechanical and electrical support.

V. SYSTEM FLOW

The connections between all of the modules and the project's loads are depicted in the diagram below. The steps or procedure to follow in order to control household appliances utilizing the IoT idea as we stated are as follows:

Fig. 4. Schematic Diagram

Fig. 5. Simulated Circuit Diagram

First and foremost, Connect the device using a USB cable, then connect the Arduino board to the computer and run the Arduino IDE programme to install the appropriate drivers. After you've opened the app, use the C language to develop a programme in the sketch window. By clicking the Tick mark on the sketch window's menu bar, we may check for problems in the programme. Then a compiled file is created and saved in the software's installation directory. In the message box below the drawing window, the path will be displayed. Now launch the ISIS Professional Proteus simulator software. Connect the circuit by dragging components from the simulator's library into place. Select OK after double-clicking on the Arduino UNO board and pasting the path into the programme file section of the edit component box. Run the simulation to ensure that the programme and circuit are working properly. Open the Arduino IDE software once more; now develop an HTML programme for the ESP 8266 module to control household appliances from smart phones. Check for faults once more, and then dump the software using the USB2.0 Micro TypeB Plug connector. The ESP 8266 module's receiver pin is connected to the Arduino board's transmitter pin, and the Arduino board's receiver pin is connected to the ESP 8266 module's transmitter pin when it comes to the hardware interface. The ESP 8266 card's receiver pin is connected to the arduino board's transmitter pin, and the ESP 8266 module's transmitter pin is connected to the arduino board's transmitter pin. The power pin of the ESP 8266 is connected to the Vin pin on the Arduino board. Each board's ground pins are shorted. Two pins of the relay module are linked to the load, and the Vin and Vcc pins of the Arduino board are linked to one of the digital pins and the 5V pin, respectively. Select the board in the port that will be in the tools button of the menu bar in the Arduino software. The yellow light blinking on the board indicates that a connection has been established between the system and the board. Now click the button on the menu bar to upload the software. Connect to the internet using WiFi. To use the website, enter your IP address. All of the load information, as well as the controlling switch, will be presented on the newly launched

homepage. We can control many home appliances with these switches.

VI. RESULT

As a result, the simulation using Arduino, ESP8266, and IoT concept household appliances may be operated as follows. Any internet-connected device can access the appliances; however, in order to open a portal for controlling the appliances, we must input the local IP address in the URL of any browser..

VII. CONCLUSION

This article uses IoT technology to mimic the automation of household appliances and discusses the benefits and drawbacks. While a Bluetooth-enabled home automation kit is versatile and affordable, it can only connect to a Bluetooth wireless network within its limited range. The ZigBee RF module was utilized in a mechanization solution to create a wireless network that allows users to remotely monitor household appliances. A GSM-based home automation framework is also being considered, in which customers may control and monitor home appliances by sending text messages from their phones. The Internet of Things is used to power home automation.

XI. REFERENCES

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